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Atlas of the *Cochylimorpha* (Razowski, 1959) species of Hungary (Lepidoptera: Tortricidae)

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Abstract. So far, 10 species of *Cochylimorpha* have been identified in Hungary. Between 1990 and 2023, the author identified hundreds of specimens by examining the genitalia. He has collected in all major natural geographic regions of the country and has conducted surveys in major museums and private collections. In this study, he summarized the data from the localities and prepared distribution maps of the species. He describes the phenology of the species, their food plants, and their preferred habitats. This is the second study in Hungary providing a summary of the *Cochylimorpha* fauna of the country. With 18 text figs, 10 distributions maps, two colour plates.

Keywords. biology, distribution, habitat, *Cochylimorpha*, Tortricidae, Hungary

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Introduction

This study aims to present the phenology, geographical distribution, and preferred habitats of all *Cochylimorpha* species identified in Hungary. This is the second publication on this topic in Hungary (see Fazekas 2022). It is part of a series of studies, which can be considered a continuation of the previous Tortricidae census. It prepares the ground for the first Hungarian summary book on Tortricidae, on which I have been working for many years.

Material and methods

I started my research in the early 1980s. For the last 40 years, I have been collecting in all-natural geographic regions of Hungary. I have studied habitats, feeding plants of species, and flight periods. The collections were mainly made with evening lights and light traps. I used mostly 160 Watt HMLI and 125-Watt mercury vapour lamps. I also collected specimens by daytime grass netting and knocking.

From 1896 to 2021, I critically processed the literature on Tortricidae species. The most important literature is given at the end of the paper. I visited and examined the most important museum and private collections in Hungary. For accurate and authentic identification, I have made thousands of genital examinations.

Genitalia dissections were made in accordance with Robinson (1976). Some of the genitalia were mounted in Euparal on slides; others are preserved in micro-vials filled with glycerol. Genital analysis of worn, damaged specimens of *Cochylimorpha* was performed using the simple and rapid method of Fazekas (2020, 2021), Wanke and Rajaei (2018).

The data of the Hungarian distribution maps are stored in a computer database, partly in Word and Excel formats.

The genital identification of the *Cochylimorpha* specimens was done by myself. My colleague Ferenc Buschmann (Jász Museum, H-Jászberény) provided an immense help in compiling the site data, to whom I would like to express my gratitude here.

Text-figs 1-2. Structural elements of the male (1) and female genitalia (2) of *Cochylimorpha* species. Highlighting the most essential elements for identification schematically. Genitalia dissections were made in accordance with Robinson (1976). Some of the genitalia were mounted in Euparal on slides. Others are preserved in micro-vials filled with glycerol.

The identified specimens are deposited in the following collections:

Bakonyi Természettudományi Múzeum, Zirc | Bakony Natural History Museum, Zirc
 Janus Pannonius Múzeum, Pécs | Janus Pannonius Museum, Pécs,
 Jász Múzeum, Jászberény | Jász Museum, Jászberény
 Magyar Természettudományi Múzeum, Budapest | Hungarian Natural History Museum, Budapest
 Mátra Múzeum, Gyöngyös | Mátra Museum, Gyöngyös
 Pannon Intézet, Pécs | Pannon Institute, Pécs,
 Rippl-Rónai Múzeum, Kaposvár | Rippl-Rónai Museum, Kaposvár
 Természettudományi Gyűjtemény, Komló | Natural History Collection, Komló

A Brief Account of Hungarian Landscape Types

I have recorded the geographical distribution of the taxa according to the six Hungarian macoregions. The geographical distribution of the taxa is exceedingly different in certain regions. On a detailed map the natural geographic landscapes of Hungary are shown with text labels and the drawing of the landscape boundaries (Text-figs 1–3.).

(I) **The Great Hungarian Plain.** Flat Plains, 75–200 m. Plain with moderately continental climate, landscape types used for agriculture. Summer microclimate of Great Hungarian Plain is more severe than that of prevalent in forested regions of Central Europe since the combination of open steppe and soda flats produces often relatively high surface temperatures during summer. Average temperatures for the plain are 22°C in July and -2°C in January. Recorded maximum and minimum extremes are about 39°C and -28°C. Natural vegetation: Oak forests and grassland on the sand, loess steppe, alkaline vegetation on solon chalk, alluvial forests, and swamps. The Hungarian plain is a typical example of the steppe or other grassland habitats favoured by many *Cochylimorpha*, as far as it is known, although the moths may prefer slight hillsides on the periphery of steppes.

This is a very large area of natural geography. Acceptable collections were conducted only near Budapest and in the "Kiskunság National Park". More thorough and planned surveys are needed.

(2) **Little Hungarian Plain** Flat plains, 75–200 m. Alluvial plain; cultivated grassland with high groundwater table and hygromorphous soils. Natural vegetation: alluvial forests and swamps, and at higher elevations oak forests and grassland on sand as well as loess steppe.

Investigations were made mainly around the city of Győr. The faunistics of this lowland along the Danube are poorly known.

(3) **West Hungarian Borderland.** Valleys, foothills, medium-height mountains with broad ridges, 150–883 m. Eroded hills in the sub-alpine regions on brown loess and pseudogleyic soils with mosaics of forests mixed with Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) partly used for agriculture, as well as eroded hills (250–350) with lessivated brown forest soil on brown loess; partly used for agriculture. Natural vegetation: mainly Illyrian oak-hornbeam forests, as well as Illyrian beech forests and oak forests, mixed with Scots pine.

Being a borderland, this region was difficult to access during the communist dictatorship before 1990. After 1990, regular or planned research was only occasional.

(4) **Transdanubian Hills** (Text-fig 5). Valleys, hills, foothills, medium-height mountains, 150–682 m. In the west fixed sandy plain with minor dunes, cultivated grassland on brown earth, local forestation, and orchards. In the east independent hilly regions dissected by eroded valleys, mostly cultivated grassland with deep groundwater table, vineyards, and major remnants of mixed forests. In the south, forested landscape types in mountains of medium height (Mecsek Mts, Villányi Mts); calcareous rock or sandstone with rendzina and lessivated brown forest soils, typically with *Tilio argenteae-Quercetum* or Illyrian oak-hornbeam forests (*Helleboro Carpinetum*), and mosaic Illyrian karst with hairy oak, karst shrub-forest and rocky swards.

This is one of the best-known natural landscapes in Hungary, with the fauna of the Mecsek and Villány Hills being particularly well-studied. In the mid-1900s, extensive research was carried out in Somogy County, especially in the Kaposvár area. It would be important to explore the valley of the River Dráva and the less-known Tolna County hills.

Text-fig. 3. Characteristic habitats and vertical distribution of *Cochylimopha* populations in Hungary: **sm**: sand meadow; **lm**: open steppe oak forests on loess; **gs**: grass steppe on hills and mountain slopes; **rg**: rocky grassy slopes; **mf**: mountain scree forest; **kf**: karst bush forests; **do**: dry, warm oak glades; **cf**: closed mesophilic forests.

Text-figs 4–6. Natural geographic landscapes and major ecological regions of Hungary based on the *Cochylimorpha* fauna: **4.** Hungarian lowlands; **5.** The hills and mountains of Transdanubia; **6.** North Hungarian Mountains and basins.

(5) **Transdanubian Mountains.** Medium-height mountains, 200–756 m. Low mountains under additional sub-Atlantic and sub-Mediterranean climatic influence. *Quercetum-petraeae-cerris* and *Quercetum-petraeae-Carpinetum* forests. Hills, in part, are dissected by eroded valleys; cultivated grassland with a mosaic of vineyards and orchards and *Quercetum-petraeae-cerris* forests and a deep groundwater table. On the mountain slopes are a variety of karst shrub forests and rock swards, e.g., in the Bakony Mts, the Vértes Mts and the Budai Mts.

From a faunistic point of view, this is the best-researched region in Hungary, especially in the Bakony and Vértes Mountains and the mountain ranges near Budapest. There are many data from the Velence Mountains and the lake area in front of them.

(6) **North Hungarian Mountains** (Text fig 6). Medium-height mountains, 300–1015 m. Extremely variable landscape type. The crests of volcanic mountains with black "nyirok" (regolith) and podsolised brown forest soil, submontane beech forests (silviculture with touristic and recreational use Mátra Mts, Zemplén Mts) feature strongly, but then so do the low mountains of calcareous rocks with rendzina and brown soil at Bükk and Aggtelek. The Bükk and Aggtelek mountains form at present a National Park. Natural vegetation: mainly *Quercetum-petraeae-cerris*, submontane oak hornbeam forests, submontane and montane beech forests, e.g., in the Mátra Mts (1015 m), in the Bükk Mts (958 m) and the Zemplén Mts (783 m).

The extensive and highly dissected mountainous area is well-explored. As there are several national parks and protected landscape areas in the region, there have been state-organized research programs in this area. The Bükk and Aggtelek National Parks are both particularly well-researched. Further studies are needed in the Börzsöny Mountains, the Zemplén Mountains and in the hilly areas and mountain basins near the Slovakian border.

Species accounts

1. *Cochylimorpha hilarana* (Herrich-Schäffer, 1851)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: Budaörs (Csíki-hegyek), Fonyód, Fülöpháza (homokbuckás), Izsák (Kolon-tó), Nagykáta, Pécs, Szentmártonkáta, *Szigetszentmiklós*, Vörs.

Biology. Adults fly from August to September in Hungary. According to Razowski (2009) they fly in July and August in the Palearctic. Foodplant: *Artemisia campestris*. Habitat: Dry grasslands and ruderal communities.

Text-figs 7–8. Left–*Cochylimorpha hilarana*; right–*Cochylimorpha halophilana*.

Text-figs 9–10. Left-*Cochylimorpha elongana*; right-*Cochylimorpha perfusana*.

Indicated characters for identification. Strigulae of *C. perfusana* form usually transverse fasciae marks. They are sometimes confused and misidentified with light coloured *C. straminea* specimens.

2. *Cochylimorpha halophilana* (Christoph, 1872)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: Farnos. Jászberény, Kenderes, Királyhegyes (Csikópuszta), Nagyiván, Nagykáta/Szentmártonkáta, Újszentmargita.

Biology. Adults fly from July to September in Hungary. Foodplant: *Artemisia* spp. Habitat: Not known, probably in dry meadows and rocky grasslands of hills and mountains.

3. *Cochylimorpha elongana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: Budafok, Budaörs (Csíki-hegyek), Budapest (Csillag-hegy, Farkas-völgy, Sas-hegy, Sváb-hegy), Farnos.

Biology. Bivoltine from May to June and August in Hungary. Foodplant: *Achillea millefolium*, *Artemisia vulgaris*, *A. campestris*, *Helichrysum arenarium*. Habitat: Dry grasslands, rocky grasslands, sandy grasslands, steppe meadows, lowland grasslands, ruderal weed communities.

Remarks. There have been no recent sightings of this species in Hungary for several decades.

4. *Cochylimorpha perfusana* (Guenée, 1845)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: No proven specimen.

Its occurrence in Hungary was reported by Gozmány (1968, 1971) as “*callosana* HS.”, and as a result, the post-millennial checklist indicated it, but no authentic Hungarian *C. perfusana* specimens are present in the Hungarian Museum of Natural History or in the other museums examined.

Buschmann (2004) reported this species in the collection of the Mátra Museum, but the specimens he deposited there (Jászberény and Nagykáta Cseh-domb) are erroneously identified *C. straminea* specimens (rev. & det. Buschmann). There is no evidence for the occurrence of this species in Hungary (pers. comm. Buschmann).

According to Razowski (2001) it is present only in Austria and the Czech Republic; it is a rare W European species, known from France and Switzerland to N Italy and Dalmatia; according to literature also Romania (Siebenbürgen).

5. *Cochylimorpha subwoliniana* (Danilevsky, 1962)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: First published in the Hungarian fauna by Tokár in 2015: Bélmegyer, Fáspuszta, 2014.V.9, 1 ♂, 1 ♀ (Gp. ♂ 12193, ♀ 12245 ZT), Zdenko Tokár leg. & coll.

Biology. According to Razowski (2009) the early stages have not been described. Adults fly in the Palaearctic from May until July. Hungarian habitat general description: *Galatello-Quercetum roboris* and *Peucedano-Asteretum sedifolii* remains in the South Tiszántúl area: The main range of the *Galatello-Quercetum roboris* and *Peucedano-Asteretum sedifolii* associations is the Tiszántúl in the Pannonian Basin. In the “Bélmegyeri Fáspuszta” (Fáspuszta=Wooded wasteland) one of the most typical stands can be found. *Peucedano-Asteretum sedifolii* community consists of meadow, grassland, and woodland species, like *Peucedanum officinale*, *Aster sedifolius*, *Aster lynosiris*, *Rumex pseudonatronatus*, *Iris spuria* (cf. Kertész 2000).

Remarks. According to Tokar (2018), the species has a wide distribution - from Central Europe to western China, but with a scattered occurrence. It has been found closest in Romania (Viișoara, Cluj; Lunca Vânjului, Mehedintți) (Rákósy et al. 2003). It has also been found in Russia [eastern and southern Europe, Central Asia, the Altai region, and western Siberia (Nupponen et al. 2001, Sinev & Nedoshivina 2008, Volynkin et al. 2011, Knyazev 2014)] and in south-eastern Kazakhstan and western China (Kuznecov 1978, Razowski 2009) [Note: Sun & Li (2013) do not mention it among the species of the genus *Cochylimorpha* occurring in China]. Its locality in Bélmegyer (Hungary) is the westernmost area known to date. Unfortunately, in many regions of the Hungarian lowlands, there have been only local studies. There is a lot of intensively farmed agricultural land. In the original continental forest-steppe remnants, fragmented *subwoliniana* population remnants are still possible, especially in protected areas and national parks, where it is hoped to observe the species.

For a definite identification, a genital examination is a good aid (see Tokár 2018): in males, *subwoliniana* can be distinguished from *woliniana* by the long and narrow end of the aedeagus and the presence of a short cornutus and only a short cornutus; in contrast to discordant, it is distinguished by the sacculus extending more strongly from the valvula and the smaller cornutus. In females, it differs from both species in having a narrow ductus bursa and only spines in the upper part of the corpus bursae, with no sclerotized parts.

Text-figs 11–12. Left–*Cochylimorpha subwoliniana*; right–*Cochylimorpha woliniana*.

Indicated characters for identification.

These two species are similar externally. A thorough genital examination is important.

(See Razowski 2009, Pl,10; Pl. 41.

Text-figs 13-14. Left—*Cochylimorpha obliquana*; right—*Cochylimorpha jucundana*. Indicated markers for identification. The *C. jucundana* is a very mysterious species in Hungary, we don't know why its detection is low.

6. *Cochylimorpha woliniana* (Schleich, 1868)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: Csopak, 1961.V.27. (1 ex), fénycsapda (light trap), Zalavári erdő–Lebujpuszta, 1950.V.8. (1 ex), VI.12. (2 ex), leg. Kaszab Z. & Székessy V. Tihany, Agárd, Sopron.

Biology. In Hungary, specimens were only collected in May and June. Foodplant: According to literature *Artemisia absinthium*. Presumably, it also survives on other species of *Artemisia*, possibly with a much broader spectrum of foodplants. Habitat based on sporadic Hungarian observations: Floodplain meadows, ruderal vegetation, cottage gardens around lakes, recreation areas, volcanic rocky steppe, rocky meadows.

Remarks. Most of the examined specimens were collected 50–60 years ago and there are no recent observations (Fazekas 2018).

7. *Cochylimorpha obliquana* (Eversmann, 1844)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: Alattyán, Apajpuszta, Budapest Csorna, Dinnyés Dömsöd, Gyoma, Farnos, Fülöpszállás, Hortobágy, Jászberény, Kenderes, Kunmadaras, Mikepércs, Nagyiván, Cserepes, Nagykáta/Szentmártonkáta, Nagykáta (Egreskáta Bata-tanya), Pákozd, Sárkeresztúr, Szeged (Szőreg), Szigetszentmiklós, Újszentmargita, Velence.

Biology. Bivoltine. Adults fly from May to June and from July to September in Hungary. Foodplant: *Artemisia santonicum*. This plant is a characteristic of continental Hungarian lowlands. Habitat: Lowland salt marshes, grasslands. Hill and mountain populations are not known.

8. *Cochylimorpha jucundana* (Treitschke, 1835)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: South Hungary, Mecsek Mountains, Pécs, 1937.VI.15. leg. J. Klimesch.

Remarks. A single specimen of this species from the above site is in the Hungarian Museum of Natural History; a second example, dated a day earlier, is in the collections of the Natural History Museum in Vienna (Fazekas 1994). No new records of the species have been made in Hungary in the last hundred years and it is presumed to be no longer present. The larval foodplant is unknown in the Hungarian data. Habitat in Hungary: former resident of limestone rocky grassland, karst scrub mosaic, a protected Natura 2000 site.

9. *Cochylimorpha straminea* (Haworth, 1811)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: Ágasegyháza, Bátorliget, Bakonybél, Balatonföldvár, Bócsa, Budafok, Budaörs (Csiki-hegyek), Budapest (Budai-hegyek), Csepel, Dinny-

Text-figs 15–16. Left–*Cochylimorpha straminea*; right–*Cochylimorpha alternana*

Indicated markers for identification.

These two species are similar but *straminea* differ from *alternana* in straight termen. of forewing and a lack of erect scale tufts in median.

és, Dömsöd (Apajpuszta), Dobogókő, Eger, Farnos, Fonyód, Gerla, Gyöngyös, Győr-Kismegyér, Harkány (Tenkes-hegy), Isaszeg, Jászberény, Jósvafő, Kaposvár, Kenderes, Kisvaszar, Kisvárd, Komló, Kőszeg, Kunszentmiklós, Makkoshotyka, Maklár, Marcali, Mát-raszentistván, Nadap, Nagyharsány, Nagyiván, Nagykáta Nagytétény, Ócsa, Ohat, Pákozd, Pásztó (Muzsla-hegy), Péczel, Pécs (Tubes), Piliscsaba, Pilisvörösvár, Kunpeszér, Simontornya, Sopron–Bánfalva, Sukoró, Sümeg, Szederkény, Szeged, Szentmártonkáta, Szentpéterföldre, Tihany, Újszász, Újszentmargita, Uzsa, Vörs, Zalavár, Zamárdi.

Biology. Bivoltine species. The first generation emerges from the end of April to mid-July and the second generation from end July to September. Widespread in Hungary, occurring up to 1000m. in mountains, where the adult flies actively amongst flower heads from dusk onwards. A eurieic species, it occurs in very dry and warm habitats, but also in cooler, more humid habitats, sometimes flying in larger numbers.

Remarks. *C. straminea* populations in sandy habitats are lighter in colour and the mid-wing brown band is rarely accompanied by dark scales, making them easily confused with *C. perfusana* (Guenée, 1845). Damaged or worn specimens in a collection can only be accurately identified by genital examination.

10. *Cochylimorpha alternana* (Stephens, 1834)

Investigated and identified localities in Hungary: Ágasegyháza, Albertirsa, Bánhida, Budafok, Budapest, Budaörs–Csiki-hegyek, Dinnyés, Epöl, Esztergom, Fót (Somlyó-hegy), Isaszeg, Kárász, Komló, Litér, Nagymaros, Tarhos.

Biology. Bivoltine. The adult flies from April to Mid-June and from July to September. Foodplant: *Centaurea scabiosa*. It is assumed that its larva lives on several *Centaurea* plants. Habitat: Dry grasslands and pastures in lowland and hilly areas. Absent from the central mountains. It has been observed on sand hills in the protected areas between the Danube and Tisza rivers and also occurs near small saline lakes.

Summary. This study analyses data from 10 *Cochylimorpha* species localities in Hungary and shows the distribution patterns of the species on maps.

The occurrence of *Cochylimorpha perfusana* in Hungary is disputed. It is said that there is an incredibly old specimen from Budapest in the Munich Museum, but this has not been examined, and if there is a specimen, it has not been identified. The specimens published from regions in the lowlands (Buschmann 2004) have been misidentified. They all turned out to be *C. straminea*.

Thus, the Hungarian *Cochylimorpha* fauna truly comprises only 9 species. Flight time data for these nine taxa are presented, as is a summary of larva foodplants, based both on personal observations and other sources. The descriptions of the habitats frequented by each species are mostly based on the present original research.

The most widespread species in Hungary is *Cochylimorpha straminea*. The taxa *C. halophilana*, *C. obliquana* and *C. alternana* are widespread, but apparently uncommon. *Cochylimorpha hilarana*, *C. elongana* and *C. woliniana* are evidently local and rare, whilst *Cochylimorpha jucundana* is presumedly extinct in this country. Many factors underlie the geographical distribution of a species, such as environmental and physical constraints, niche demand or trophic position, population abundance, colonization-extinction dynamics, adaptation, etc.

Cochylimorpha subwolniana stands out as a single isolated occurrence in Eastern Hungary at the westernmost limit of its range. It may have colonised the Pannonian basin from Romania in the postglacial period. From a phylogenetic point of view, this species requires more detailed studies.

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Text-fig 17. The main functional hierarchical levels of landscape characters in the study of *Cochylimorpha* species.

Text-fig. 18. Idealized geomorphological and habitat types of Hungary with characteristic *Cochylimorpha* species.

Fig. 1. Distribution of *Cochylimorpha hilarana* in Hungary

Fig. 2. Distribution of *Cochylimorpha halophilana* in Hungary

Fig. 3. Distribution of *Cochyliomorpha elongana* in Hungary

Fig. 4. Distribution of *Cochyliomorpha perfusana* in Hungary

Fig. 5. Distribution of *Cochylimorpha subwolniana* in Hungary

Fig. 6. Distribution of *Cochylimorpha wolniana* in Hungary

Fig. 7. Distribution of *Cochyliomorpha obliquana* in Hungary

Fig. 8. Distribution of *Cochyliomorpha jucundana* in Hungary

Fig. 9. Distribution of *Cochylimorpha straminea* in Hungary

Fig. 10. Distribution of *Cochylimorpha alternana* in Hungary

Fig. 11. Techniques and tools for personal collections with light: light sources used: 125 Watt mercury vapour lamp and 160 Watt HLMI lamp.

Plate 1. The pattern of forewings and hindwings at different magnifications:
Cochylimorpha hilarana; 2. *C. halophilana*; 3. *C. elongana*; 4. *C. perfusana*;
5. *C. subwoliana*; 6. *C. woliana*.

Plate 2. The pattern of forewings and hindwings at different magnifications:
 7. *Cochylimorpha obliquana*; 8. *C. jucundana*; 9. *C. straminea*; 10. *C. alternana*.

List of *Cochylimorpha* species identified so far in Hungary:

1. *Cochylimorpha hilarana* (Herrich-Schäffer, [1815])
2. *Cochylimorpha halophilana* (Christoph, 1872)
3. *Cochylimorpha elongana* (Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1839)
4. *Cochylimorpha perfusna* (Guenée, 1845)
5. *Cochylimorpha subwoliniana* (Danilevsky, 1962)
6. *Cochylimorpha woliniana* (Schleich, 1868)
7. *Cochylimorpha obliquana* (Eversmann, 1844)
8. *Cochylimorpha jucundana* (Treitschke, 1835)
9. *Cochylimorpha straminea* (Haworth, 1811)
10. *Cochylimorpha alternana* (Curtis, 1831)

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